

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Digital literacy to improve the quality of state civil apparatus services for the of Indonesia community

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Abstract

Extraordinary technological developments have also impacted changes in public services with the use of digital technology in the mechanism of providing public services to the community. Indonesia's desire to become a developed country forces Indonesia to make changes in serving its people, one of which is through digital technology. This research uses a qualitative approach through a descriptive analysis method based on the literature study obtained and then used as analysis material. This study aims to analyze the concept of practical digital literacy in accordance with the application of the quality of public services in Government, especially for the state civil apparatus. There is a digital-based public service design that can be implemented thoroughly for the community and, of course, makes it easier for the community as beneficiaries. The results of this study explain the analysis of eight aspects of digital literacy, which are elaborated with the parameters of the elements of assessing the quality of public government services which can then be used as a design of an integrated digital-based service system.

Keywords: Digital Literacy; Quality of Service; State Civil Apparatus; Indonesia Community

1. Introduction

The outbreak of Covid-19 has brought tremendous changes to bureaucratic governance. Implementation of Work From Home (WFH) in various agencies in transforming public services from manual (conventional) models to digital services to improve services to the community [1]. There are three models of public services during the Covid-19 pandemic that apply in several government agencies and can be used as examples. First, public services are running as usual, but the State Civil Apparatus and applicants must implement Covid-19 prevention protocols, such as physical distancing. Second, direct assistance is combined with online service, with schedule sharing for State Civil Apparatus who work at home and in the office. Third, public services are online only.

Changes in the work system implemented to have an impact on the use of supporting facilities for every work carried out by State Civil Apparatus. The transformation of the working mechanism required based on the direction of the Ministerial Regulation of the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform Number 25 of 2021 concerning Simplification of Organizational Structure in Government Agencies for Bureaucratic Simplification is a working system that adheres to the business process principles of State Civil Apparatus employees by utilizing an electronic-based government system Regulation of the Minister of Administrative Reform & Bureaucratic Reform Number 25 of 2021 Concerning Simplification of Organizational Structures in Government Agencies to Simplify Bureaucracy.

In line with this, according to Presidential Regulation No. 95 of 2018 concerning Electronic-Based Government Systems. Electronic-Based Government Systems defining is a government administration that utilizes information and communication technology to provide services to Electronic-Based Government Systems Users, where Electronic-Based

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Government Systems users are Central Agencies, Regional Governments, State Civil Apparatus employees, individuals, communities, business actors, and other parties who utilize Electronic-Based Government Systems Services. Comprehensively, the electronic-based government system provides space for each Agency, both Central and Regional, to map the duties and functions of each work unit and its employees that support full work goals by developing ideal work mechanisms in supporting agency performance goals and improving the quality of public services. However, the fact is that this implementation is not optimal, especially since there are still several agencies that have not implemented Electronic-Based Government Systems services as quoted [2] on the “Kompas” newspaper page; there are several complaints from the public regarding public services as attached to the following picture:

Source: Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform, 2020

Figure 1 Public Service Complaints

The picture above shows that there were 348 complaints received by the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform. Population administration services ranked highest with 153 complaints. The electrical service of 116 complaints became the second highest rank. Tax services ranked third with 40 complaints. Licensing services and immigration services ranked fifth and sixth with 20 and 11 complaints, respectively, and oil and gas with eight complaints. This data reflects the suboptimal public services provided by the Government during 2020 due to changes in the work system for State Civil Apparatus during the Covid-19 Pandemic, which are not adjusted to the development of technological infrastructure in providing public services in the Government.

Indonesia's ideal of becoming one of the countries in the ranks of developed countries requires government policies in public services to the community because one of the characteristics of developed countries is the guarantee of the welfare of their people's lives. The development of the times that are currently in the era of digital society 5.0 cannot be separated from the aspect of public services [3].

Public services also need a change in the way of bureaucratic reform. Bureaucratic reform in the era of digital society 5.0 means efforts to make fundamental updates in the system of government administration in the human resources of its apparatus to realize the welfare of the Indonesian people as well as a process of introducing digitalization to Indonesian society in this digital society 5.0 era [3]. The development of the digital society 5.0 generation also has a reasonably complicated impact on problems in society that make public service complex.

The need for Indonesia to make updates in public services is also due to the multidimensional crisis that has occurred in Indonesian society. The quality of human resources in the era of digital society also plays an important role in advancing the nation because how can this nation make the right policies for public services if it does not have quality apparatus human resources [4], [5]. There is an improvement in services by having the quality of service, which is an important issue in the provision of public services in Indonesia. Public service opinion has always been an image attached to service providers in Indonesia. So far, public service has always been synonymous with inaction, injustice, and high costs. Not to mention in terms of service ethics, where the behavior of service providers is not expressive and does not reflect the spirit of good service. According to [6], Government officials carry out government activities, encourage accountability to the community, the community, and public service providers, and advance telecommunications. The quality of service itself can be represented as a dynamic condition related to products, services, people, processes, and the environment that meets or exceeds expectations. Furthermore, the dynamism of the needs of one's own society. According to [7] because the rapid changes in world life have a rapid influence on changes in attitudes and behaviors of society in general.

Based on the explanation above, the writing of this article raises the issue of problems regarding digital literacy in improving the quality of public services by prioritizing essential aspects so that it can provide an overview of the implementation of digital-based public services in the Government as a whole that is effective and adapts to the needs of a dynamic society in accordance with the targets of the Government's policy direction.

The introduction should be typed in Cambria with font size 10. Author can select Normal style setting from Styles of this template. The simplest way is to replace (copy-paste) the content with your own material. In this section highlight the importance of topic, making general statements about the topic and presenting an overview on current research on the subject. Your introduction should clearly identify the subject area of interest.

1.1 Problem Formulation

Based on the background above, problems can be formulated from writing this article, namely: How is the design required from the aspects of digital literacy in compiling an effective improvement in the quality of public services in Government Agencies by adjusting to the dynamism of community needs?

2. Literature Review

2.1 Digital Literacy

Digital literacy is the knowledge and skills of users in utilizing digital media, such as communication tools, internet networks, and so on. User proficiency in digital literacy includes the ability to find, do, evaluate, use, create and utilize it wisely, intelligently, meticulously, and precisely according to its usefulness [8].

Digital literacy is more associated with the technical skills of accessing, stringing, understanding, and disseminating information [9]. Then according to [10] in [11], digital literacy is defined as the ability to understand and use information in various forms, be it audio or visual from a very wide range of sources accessed through computer devices or digitization. So whatever form of information we receive through a computer or digital is called digital literacy.

So based on the expert opinion above, it can be stated that digital literacy is an understanding and mindset of the informer/informant in using media facilities and technological infrastructure facilities to distribute accurate information that is needed for information recipients. Understanding and mindset are essential for two parties as a liaison in channeling information so that it is conveyed clearly. According to [12], [13], Digital literacy is a combination of several forms of literacy, namely: computers, information, technology, visuals, media, and communication. With these six basic literacy skills, [12] formulated the following dimensions of digital literacy:

- Digital literacy involves digital action skills tied to work, learning, fun, and other aspects of everyday life.
- Individual digital literacy varies depending on the daily situation they are experiencing and the lifelong process of the individual's life situation.
- Digital literacy involves the ability to collect and use knowledge, techniques, attitudes, and personal qualities in addition to the ability to plan, execute and evaluate digital actions as part of solving problems/tasks in life.
- Digital literacy also involves a person's awareness of their level of digital literacy and the development of digital literacy.

Based on the principles of computer and information literacy, according to [14], Develop a more comprehensive digital literacy concept by involving the following aspects:

- Knowledge assembly is the ability to build information from various trusted sources.
- The ability to present information includes critical thinking in understanding information with the vigilance of the validity and completeness of sources from the internet.
- Ability to read and understand non-sequential and dynamic information materials.
- Awareness of the importance of conventional media and connecting it with networked media (internet).
- Awareness of access to a network of people that can be used as a source of referral and help.
- Use of sieves against incoming information.
- Feel comfortable and have access to publish information.

Meanwhile, [15] says that there are eight essential elements to developing digital literacy, which is as follows:

- Cultural, namely understanding the various contexts of users of the digital world;
- Cognitive, that is, the power of thought in assessing content;
- Constructive, that is, the creation of something expert and actual;

- Communicative, that is, understanding the performance of networks and communication in the digital world;
- Responsible self-confidence;
- Creative, doing new things in new ways;
- Critical in responding to content; and digital literacy as life skills;
- Socially responsible.

The explanation of the essential elements above is a fundamental element in the development of digital literacy. With digital literacy, it is hoped that it can better understand and be able to have abilities in cognitive and communicative terms. Through the description of the essential elements above, it can be concluded that the urgency side of the implementation of digital literacy includes several aspects, namely cultural, cognitive, constructive, communicative, confident, creative, critical, and responsible elements with supporting parts, namely knowledge, techniques and attitudes that synergize with each other in providing information between both parties, both informants and recipients of the information.

2.2 Public Service

Public service, according to [16], is the fulfillment of the wants and needs of society by state organizers. While based on the Decree Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform Number 63 of 2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services, the definition of public services is any form of service carried out by Government Agencies at the Center, Regions, and within the Environment of State-Owned Enterprises or Regional-Owned Enterprises in the form of goods and or services, both in the context of efforts to meet the needs of the community and in the context of implementing the provisions of laws and regulations.

In line with this, according to [17], Public service is the provision of services, either by the Government, private parties on behalf of the Government, or private parties to the community with or without payment to meet the needs and or interests of the community. Thus, those who provide public services to the wider community are not only government agencies but also private parties.

So it can be concluded that public services are activities carried out by government agencies both at the center, in the regions, and within state-owned or regional enterprises to provide services to the community in the context of implementing statutory provisions and meeting the needs of the community.

2.3 Principles and Principles of Public Service Quality

Theoretically, the purpose of public service is basically to accommodate the needs of the community. In order to accommodate these needs, excellent and professional public service quality is required. Here are the principles in public service according to [16] that is:

- Transparency
- Accountability
- Conditional
- participatory
- Equal Rights
- Balance of Rights and Obligations

In the process of service activities, it is also regulated regarding the principle of service as a reference basis in supporting the course of actions. The principles of public service according to the Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 of 2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services include:

- Simplicity
- Clarity
- Certainty of time
- accuracy
- Security
- Responsibility
- Complete facilities and infrastructure
- Ease of access
- Discipline, courtesy, and friendliness
- Convenience

With the explanation above, it can be used as a benchmark for improving the quality of public services in making a major contribution to the needs of an effective and transparent society. The service process that is regulated based on these points clarifies the steps for each Government Agency in providing services through guidance and procedures that have been established by regulations. However, in the current paradigm, the needs of a very dynamic society require an innovation carried out by the Government as a public service. The Government is also required to apply the principle of equity, meaning that government services should not be provided in a discriminatory manner. Services are provided regardless of the status, rank, class of the community, and all citizens have the same rights to these services in accordance with applicable regulations. The procedures and principles of the quality of such public services would be better followed up by elaborating [18].

3. Research methods

The research method used is a qualitative approach through a descriptive analysis method based on the literature study obtained and then used as analytical material in compiling public service designs based on digital literacy to answer the formulation of the problem above. The literature sources used are books, research articles, and articles in online mass media related to digital literacy and the quality of public services.

4. Results and discussion

Quality of public services, according to [19], can be measured through three elements. Namely, the first element is the service provider organization, namely the Government / Local Government. The second element is the recipient of the service (customer), namely the person or community, or organization concerned, and the third element is the satisfaction given and/or received by the recipient of the service (customer). This parameter will be used as a reference for analysis in preparing digital literacy-based service designs.

Some aspects of digital literacy that are used as the basis for analysis are cultural, cognitive, constructive, communicative, confident, creative, critical, and socially responsible aspects [15]. Then the analysis of each aspect of digital literacy will be viewed from the point of view of the elements of public services consisting of the giver (Government), recipient (community), and the satisfaction provided. The analysis will be explained in detail as follows:

4.1 Cultural aspects

Cultural aspects related to culture, a culture that prevails in the environment of the state civil apparatus where elements of curiosity and understanding of the variety of digital worlds are built with a supportive ecosystem of prevailing cultures. The concern of a leader towards his subordinates by sharing knowledge, especially in technology-related sciences will help their daily tasks as well as in the context of the digital world, which is again the current trend. As recipients, the public is also given knowledge on how to use digital media in public services so that the public can better understand and can use it.

4.2 Cognitive aspects

This cognitive aspect of the civil apparatus of the state government can identify the understanding of digital content as something that is very important to apply and, of course, also useful to society. Here State Civil Apparatus as an extension of the Government, must be able to implement the quality of customer service optimally to people in need. For the community itself, a forum is created on how to accommodate their complaints, and will be evaluated for even better services. People must feel satisfied with the services provided by looking at the service needs they want.

4.3 Constructive aspects

This constructive aspect is where the Government can cooperate with third parties, such as private parties, in implementing digital systems. The Government must ensure that the right service is concrete to the community. People must feel that digital services really make it easier for them, and the community also feels the services provided, in this case, State Civil Apparatus, are really optimal for them.

4.4 Communicative aspect

The communicative aspect is an understanding of the performance and process of using the system necessary for the state civil apparatus through educational and training programs provided in accordance with the types of services that exist. One of the things that can be done through training that it will improve State Civil Apparatus skills in using the system. For the public, it is necessary to provide a form of brief information on each type of service regarding the

understanding of procedures for using the system to ensure that the results of public services are in accordance with what is proposed. The satisfaction side will work well if these two aspects can be implemented continuously.

4.5 Responsible self-confidence aspects

This aspect of the high leadership in the Government can provide delegates of tasks to admins and users of the division of each authority as users of the service system, which is adjusted to their respective levels. On the community side, socialization can be given, which is appealing and persuasive so that the public can easily understand the digital service system used to increase the positive stigma against the quality of digital-based services. The community will accept the satisfaction side if the community's perception has been formed as a whole towards the use of digital-based services.

4.6 Creative aspects

This aspect of creativity can be stimulated through employee exchanges or comparative studies of employees in the Government with the private sector or in foreign regions that have implemented the concept of digital-based services with good capabilities. This aspect of creativity can also reduce employee saturation in doing daily work and also as a way to improve their knowledge in the digital world. A high level of creativity can be obtained when the response from the community to the need for services is increasingly dynamic and positive, of course. Therefore, the types of services needed are expected to be collected thoroughly at the planning stage of the development of the digital service system used.

4.7 Critical aspects

In this aspect, the Government can carry out a monitoring and evaluation program for the implementation of digitalization of public services that have been implemented. The Government can do benefits and risks with the use of digital technology. The Government must minimize the risks and maximize the benefits for users, who, in this case, are the people. The follow-up afterward of all the systems that have been built can be integrated with each other so that the receiving side (the community) can easily obtain information through integrated services. Then in terms of satisfaction, it can be done from the integration of systems that are implemented comprehensively and systemically with no overlap of each type of service that exists.

4.8 Socially responsible aspects

This aspect, both from the Government and the community, can conduct social forums by stimulating and inviting an open level of cooperation regarding each other's moral responsibility as users and beneficiaries of the service system provided so that both parties benefit from the use of the service system digitally.

The results of the analysis above can be concluded that successful digital-based services must have good cooperation between the users in this case the Government and the community as the beneficiary. The Government involving third parties, namely private parties, in assisting the implementation of this digital service program is also very important because the private sector can help in implementing a digital system between the user and the party who receives the benefits.

5. Conclusion

The transformation of public services that switch to digital is indeed worth doing because of the current technological developments that cannot be contained anymore. The development of ordinary quartz technology can certainly facilitate human work, which initially manually takes a long time and high costs because the process is quite long. However, with the existence of technology, the amount of cost and length of time can be reduced to a minimum with the help of technology. Therefore, the use of digital technology in services to the community is appropriate, and it's just that it takes time and adjustments in its application both as users, namely the Government, and the community as parties who receive benefits.

Improving the quality of digital-based public services can be implemented in eight aspects, namely: cultural, cognitive, constructive, communicative, confident, creative, critical, and socially responsible aspects. Then the analysis of each aspect of digital literacy will be viewed from the point of view of the elements of public services consisting of the giver (Government), recipient (community), and the satisfaction provided. The results of this analysis explain that the role of both parties, both the Government and the community, is essential to ensure the continuity of the quality of adequate public services.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

We, the research team, state that there is no conflict of interest in publishing the results of this study.

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